

Mahatma Gandhi's Sarvodaya Philosophy: Relevance and Application in the 21st Century

Akshay Kumar* Nidhi Saini* Purshottam**

*Research Scholar **Assistant Professor

Department of Social Work,

Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana, India

Abstract- The paper delves into the profound philosophical concept of Sarvodaya as favored by Mahatma Gandhi, exploring its historical roots, philosophical underpinnings, and contemporary relevance. Sarvodaya, meaning “the welfare of all” embodies Gandhi’s vision of holistic societal progress that transcends conventional notions of development. The paper begins by providing a historical context, examining the socio-political landscape during Gandhi’s time, and the impetus that led him to formulate the concept of Sarvodaya. Gandhi’s experiences, influenced by both Eastern and Western philosophies, shaped his conviction that true progress could only be achieved when the welfare of the most vulnerable members of society was prioritized.

Keywords: Sarvodaya, Welfare, Upliftment, Contemporary.

➤ **Introduction**

Sarvodaya, a term coined by Mahatma Gandhi, translates to “the welfare of all” or “universal upliftment.” Gandhi envisioned a society where every individual, regardless of their background, would experience progress and well-being. This concept is rooted in the principles of non-violence, truth, and equality. Gandhi believed that true development could only occur when it benefited everyone in society, especially the marginalized and underprivileged. He emphasized the idea of self-sufficiency at the community level, encouraging decentralized, village-based economies. The goal was to create a harmonious and just society where each person’s needs were met, and no one was left behind. Sarvodaya also underscores the importance of moral and spiritual values in governance and social structures. Gandhi’s vision was not just about economic development but aimed at the holistic well-being of individuals and communities. In essence, Sarvodaya reflects Gandhi’s philosophy of achieving progress through non-violent means, ensuring that the fruits of development are distributed equitably, and promoting a way of life that values simplicity, truth, and compassion.

➤ **Historical Context**

The concept of Sarvodaya has its deep root in Indian Philosophical traditions. The concept has been used as “good will to all” (Sarva mangal bhavana) in both the Vedantic and Buddhist traditions. For the first time, in the history of Indian Philosophy, Acharya Samantbhadra, a Jain philosopher, used the concept “Sarvodaya Tirth” in his book, Yuktyanushasan. He brought the term as an adjective or the substitute for the whole of the teachings of Lord Mahavira, constituting the principles of manifoldness of reality (Anekantvad) and relativity of knowledge which emancipate all from suffering and lead to

salvation. Here the “Sarvodaya tirtha” means ‘the spiritual upliftment of all’. It had little concern with the socio-economic, and other mundane welfare of the people. Its chief stress was on non-violence universal-which includes all living beings, great or small. In Advait Vedant, particularly, in the philosophy of Shankaracharya, Sarvodaya is not ‘welfare of all’ but realization of one absolute in all-that is salvation. There are Sarvodayaelements in Bible which inspired Ruskin. Tolstoy and others, but there is no ideology or principles of Sarvodaya in dear form.

Sarvodaya, a term coined by Mahatma Gandhi, translates to "the welfare of all" or "universal uplift." Gandhi's concept of Sarvodaya was deeply rooted in his philosophy of non-violence (ahimsa) and his vision for a just and equitable society.

This idea emerged in the early 20th century, during India's struggle for independence from British colonial rule. Gandhi was a key figure in the Indian independence movement, and his approach was unique in its emphasis on non-violent resistance and the pursuit of social justice. Sarvodaya represented Gandhi's vision for a society where everyone would experience progress and well-being, and it went beyond political independence to encompass economic, social, and moral dimensions. Gandhi believed in decentralized, self-sustaining communities where individuals would work together for the common good. He envisioned a society where the welfare of the weakest and most vulnerable members was prioritized. The concept also emphasized the importance of truth, non-violence, and the dignity of labor. Sarvodaya had a profound influence on various social and political movements, both in India and globally. It inspired leaders and activists to adopt non-violent means for social change and to prioritize the well-being of all members of society.

It was Gandhi, in, modern times, who for the first time coined the term ‘Sarvodaya’ paraphrasing Ruskin’s “unto this last” in Gujarati language and evolved from it an entire ideology of Sarvodaya. As, he was assassinated in the very dawn of India’s political freedom, he could not develop the principles of Sarvodaya in detail which was fulfilled by Acharya Vinoda Bhave through his Sarvodaya movement and followed by Jaiprakash Narayan and other contemporaries of Gandhi and Vinoda.

➤ **Principles of Sarvodaya**

Gandhi's Sarvodaya is rooted in the principles of non-violence (Ahimsa), truth (Satya), selflessness (Nishkama Karma), and the welfare of all (Sarvodaya). Here are some key principles associated with Gandhi's Sarvodaya:

1. **Ahimsa (Non-violence):** Central to Gandhi's philosophy, ahimsa advocates for the avoidance of harm to any living being. It extends beyond physical violence to include non-violence in thought, speech, and action.
2. **Sarvodaya (Welfare of All):** The core principle, Sarvodaya emphasizes the well-being and upliftment of all members of society, especially the marginalized and disadvantaged.
3. **Satyagraha (Truth Force):** Gandhi believed in the power of truth and advocated for nonviolent resistance to injustice. Satyagraha is the pursuit of truth through nonviolent means, even in the face of oppression.

4. **Swadeshi (Self-sufficiency):** Gandhi promoted the idea of economic self-sufficiency at the local level. He encouraged the use of local resources and the production of goods within communities to reduce dependence on external sources.

5. **Decentralization:** Sarvodaya supports decentralized decision-making and governance. Gandhi believed in the importance of local self-governance, where communities have the power to make decisions that affect them.

6. **Sarva Dharma Sambhava (Equal Respect for All Religions):** Gandhi advocated for religious tolerance and believed in the equal validity of all religions. He emphasized the need for mutual respect and understanding among people of different faiths.

7. **Simple Living:** Gandhi practiced and promoted a simple and frugal lifestyle. He believed in the value of moderation and self-discipline, encouraging people to live with only what is necessary.

8. **Constructive Programmes:** Gandhi believed in addressing social issues through constructive programs such as education, sanitation, and rural development. These programs aimed to build a stronger and self-reliant society from within. These principles collectively form the foundation of Gandhi's vision of Sarvodaya, envisioning a society where justice, equality, and non-violence prevail, and the welfare of all is prioritized.

Sarvodaya, meaning "the welfare of all" in Sanskrit, is a philosophy that advocates for the well-being and upliftment of all individuals in society. Here are some applications of Sarvodaya:

➤ **Applications of Sarvodaya**

1. **Community Development:** Implementing Sarvodaya principles involves focusing on the holistic development of communities. This can include initiatives such as education programs, healthcare services, and economic development projects that benefit the entire community.

2. **Social Justice:** Sarvodaya emphasizes equality and social justice. Its application involves working towards a society where all individuals have equal opportunities and rights, regardless of their background or social status.

3. **Rural Development:** In many cases, Sarvodaya principles are applied in rural development projects. This could involve sustainable agriculture practices, access to clean water, and empowering rural communities through education and skill development.

4. **Non-Violence and Peace:** Sarvodaya is closely associated with the principles of non-violence. Promoting peace and resolving conflicts through dialogue and understanding is a key application of Sarvodaya.

5. **Cooperative Movements:** Sarvodaya encourages the establishment of cooperatives where individuals work together for mutual benefit. This could be in the form of agricultural cooperatives, cooperative banks, or other collective endeavors.

6. **Education for All:** A crucial aspect of Sarvodaya is providing education to all members of society. This includes efforts to eliminate barriers to education and ensure that everyone, regardless of their socio-economic background, has access to quality education.

7. **Environmental Sustainability:** Sarvodaya can be applied to promote sustainable development practices that consider the long-term well-being of both current and future generations. This includes environmental conservation and responsible resource management.

8. **Healthcare for All:** Ensuring access to healthcare services for all members of society aligns with Sarvodaya principles. This involves not only treating illnesses but also promoting preventive healthcare and overall well-being.

9. **Empowerment of Women:** Sarvodaya emphasizes gender equality and the empowerment of women. Applications in this context involve initiatives that promote women's education, economic independence, and participation in decision-making processes.

10. **Global Citizenship:** Sarvodaya is not limited to a specific geographic location and can be applied on a global scale. Efforts to address global issues such as poverty, inequality, and climate change align with the principles of Sarvodaya.

In essence, the applications of Sarvodaya are diverse and can be adapted to various contexts to promote the overall welfare and upliftment of individuals and communities.

➤ **Criticisms and challenges**

1. **Idealism vs Realism:** Critics argue that Sarvodaya is often seen as an idealistic concept that may not be easily achievable in the real world. The gap between the ideal and the practical implementation poses a significant challenge.

2. **Cultural and Regional Variation:** The applicability of Sarvodaya may vary across different cultures and regions. What works in one context may not necessarily work in another, and critics contend that a one-size-fits-all approach may not be effective.

3. **Economic Viability:** Some critics question the economic viability of Sarvodaya, arguing that the emphasis on equal distribution of resources and wealth may not be sustainable in the long run. They raise concerns about the potential negative impact on economic growth and innovation.

4. **Human Nature and Self-Interest:** Critics argue that Sarvodaya assumes a level of altruism and selflessness among individuals that may not align with human nature. The inherent self-interest of individuals might pose challenges to the idea of prioritizing the welfare of all.

5. **Political Challenges:** Implementing Sarvodaya requires political will and cooperation. Political instability, corruption, and power struggles can hinder efforts to achieve the goals of Sarvodaya.

6. **Lack of Specific Policy Guidelines:** Critics argue that Sarvodaya is often presented as a broad philosophy without clear, concrete policy guidelines. This lack of specificity can make it challenging to implement and measure progress.

7. **Resistance to Change:** Implementing Sarvodaya may face resistance from established power structures, economic interests, and societal norms. Overcoming these resistances can be a significant challenge.

8. **Education and Awareness:** The success of Sarvodaya

depends on the education and awareness of the population. Critics argue that inadequate education and awareness may limit the acceptance and understanding of the principles underlying Sarvodaya.

It's important to note that while there are criticisms, there are also supporters of the Sarvodaya philosophy who believe in its potential to create a more just and equitable society. The challenges mentioned here should be considered in the context of ongoing discussions and debates surrounding social and economic ideologies.

➤ **Relevance in Contemporary Times**

Sarvodaya, meaning "the welfare of all" in Sanskrit, is a concept rooted in the idea of universal upliftment and social harmony. While it originated in the context of the Indian independence movement, its relevance extends to contemporary times as well. In today's world, where global interconnectedness is both a boon and a challenge, the principles of Sarvodaya can offer valuable insights. The emphasis on inclusive development, social justice, and the well-being of all aligns with the goals of creating a more equitable and sustainable society. In the face of modern challenges such as economic disparities, environmental concerns, and social divisions, the Sarvodaya philosophy encourages us to consider the broader impact of our actions. It promotes a sense of responsibility towards the welfare of not just a specific community or nation, but the entire global community. Incorporating Sarvodaya principles into contemporary discourse can inspire individuals and societies to work towards solutions that benefit everyone, fostering a sense of interconnectedness and shared responsibility. It serves as a reminder that progress and development should be pursued in a way that leaves no one behind and ensures the well-being of the entire human family.

➤ **Conclusion**

Gandhi's concept of Sarvodaya, meaning "the welfare of all," encapsulates a profound vision for a just and harmonious society. Rooted in the principles of non-violence, truth, and selflessness, Sarvodaya emphasizes the upliftment of every individual, ensuring that no one is left behind. Gandhi envisioned a world where social and economic progress is not achieved at the expense of others but is inclusive and sustainable. Sarvodaya calls for the eradication of poverty, the promotion of equality, and the recognition of the interconnectedness of all beings. It is a holistic approach that addresses not only the material well-being of individuals but also their spiritual and moral development. The philosophy of Sarvodaya challenges us to reevaluate our priorities, moving away from selfish pursuits and embracing a more compassionate and collective mindset. It underscores the idea that true progress is measured by the well-being of the weakest and most vulnerable members of society.

In conclusion, Gandhi's Sarvodaya is a timeless and relevant concept that urges us to strive for a world where justice, equality, and compassion guide our actions. It invites us to build a society where the dignity of every individual is upheld, and the pursuit of a common good takes precedence over individual interests. Embracing Sarvodaya is not just a tribute to Gandhi's legacy but a commitment to creating a better, more equitable world for future generations.

Reference

1. Das, G. History of Social Thought, New Delhi, FBD, 1994, p.267-69.
2. Kumar, R. GANDHI'S APPROACH TO SARVODAYA. 2017
3. M.K.Gandhi: Village Swaraj; Navjivan publishing House, Ahamadabad
4. Nanda, B. Indian Political Traditions, Cuttack, Banirupa, 1989, p.142-45.
5. Singh, M.K. & Kumar, A. Reading Gandhi, New Delhi, 2007, p. 80-91.
6. Vettickal, T. V. (1998). *Sarvodaya of Mahatma Gandhi, realistic utopia* (Doctoral dissertation).